

Estimate the peak load and perforation energy of fibre metal laminates subjected to low velocity impact

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Abstract

In this paper, using the validated finite element models, a series of parametric study results of fibre metal laminates subjected to low velocity impact were presented. This covers influences of target size, target thickness, projectile size and projectile striking angle on the peak load and perforation energy. Based on these parametric study results and Timoshenko's theory, empirical formulas for circular or square plates impacted perpendicularly at the target centre by hemi-spherical projectile were developed. The calculated results from the empirical formulas were compared with experimental results and numerical simulations. Good correlation was obtained in terms of load-displacement traces up to the peak load and the peak load and perforation energy. The formulas developed may be used to assist design of fibre metal laminates subjected to low velocity impact.

1 Introduction

Fibre metal laminates (FMLs) are multi-layered materials based on stacked arrangements of aluminium alloy and fibre-reinforced composite materials. Currently, FMLs such as GLARE (glass fibre/aluminium) and CALL (carbon fibre/aluminium) are attracting the interest of a number of aircraft manufacturers. For example, the aramid fibre/epoxy system, ARALL, is presently being used in the manufacture of the cargo door of the American C-17 transport aircraft whilst GLARE is being used in the manufacture of the upper fuselage of the A380 [1, 2], an aircraft that is capable of carrying up to 700 passengers.

Research on FMLs subjected to low velocity impact has been undertaken extensively. There are mainly three approaches and their combinations, (1)

experimental tests, (2) theoretical analysis and (3) numerical modelling. Numerous studies have demonstrated that FMLs combine the superior fatigue and fracture characteristics associated with fiber-reinforced composite materials, with the durability offered by many metals [2-5]. The analytical approach is mainly based on the conventional plate or laminate theories and evolved from experimental results and/or numerical simulations. However, it is very difficult to describe accurately the phenomena occurring during impact [6, 7]. Under low velocity circumstances, the progression of damage in a polymeric matrix laminate is usually made of intralaminar cracks in the matrix, fibre failures, and delamination. In FMLs, the presence of metal sheets, prone to large plastic deformations and tearing, further complicates the task [8-10]. Caprino *et al.* [11, 12] provided a simple way to approach the problem of low velocity impact response of FMLs. Numerical modelling of FMLs subjected to low velocity impact using finite element approach has also been carried out extensively [13-15].

In this paper, using the validated finite element models, a series of parametric study results of fibre metal laminates subjected to low velocity impact were presented. This covers influences of target size, target thickness, projectile size and projectile striking angle on the peak load and perforation energy. Based on these parametric study results and Timoshenko's theory, empirical formulas for circular or square plates impacted perpendicularly at the target centre by hemi-spherical projectile were developed. The calculated results from the empirical formulas were compared with experimental results and numerical simulations. Good correlation was obtained in terms of load-displacement traces up to the peak load and the peak load and perforation energy. The formulas developed may be used to

assist design of fibre metal laminates subjected to low velocity impact.

2 Parametric studies

Parametric studies were carried out on fibre metal laminates subjected to low velocity impact using the validated finite element models [15]. The influences of target size, target thickness and projectile size on the peak load are considered.

A series of parametric studies were undertaken on circular 2/1 and 3/2 FMLs based on 4-ply composite cores with various plate diameters impacted at their centre by a hemispherical projectile with a diameter of 10 mm. FE models were developed for 72 mm × 72 mm square 2/1, 3/2, 4/3, 5/4 and 6/5 FMLs impacted at the centre by a hemispherical projectile with a diameter of 10mm. The effect of projectile size on impact response was also investigated on 72 mm × 72 mm square 2/1 and 3/2 FMLs (based on 4-ply composite cores). Here only the relationships between the peak load/perforation energy and target size for 2/1 (4-ply) and 3/2 (4-ply) FMLs are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Relationship between the peak load/perforation energy and the target size for the 2/1 and 3/2 FML plates.

3 Development of empirical formulae

Based on the strain energy method originally provided by Timoshenko and the equation proposed by Caprino *et al.* [16, 17], the load P for the 3/2

Fig. 2. Relationship between the peak load/perforation energy and the thickness of FMLs for FMLs based on 4-ply composite cores subjected to low velocity impact, data from FE simulations.

In addition, Fig. 2 gives the variation of the peak load and the perforation energy with the thickness of the FMLs for 2/1, 3/2, 4/3, 5/4 and 6/5 FMLs based on 4-ply composite cores. There were drastic increases in both the peak load and the perforation energy with increasing thickness of the FML. Such increases are highly nonlinear and follow a power law. The increase in the perforation energy is certainly more significant than the increase on the peak load.

FMLs is assumed to be expressed as:

$$P = C \frac{A}{B} \frac{Eh}{a^2} w^2 + D \frac{1}{B} \frac{Eh^3}{a} w \quad (1)$$

where w is the displacement at centre, h is the thickness of the plate, P is the load, a is the plate

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diameter, E is the effective elastic modulus of fibre metal laminates, and A and B are constants related to boundary conditions. $C=0.0015$ m and $D=15$ m⁻¹, based on the impact results of the circular FMLs with diameters of 50, 100 and 150mm. C may be taken as equivalent to a deflection and D as a curvature related to the side length or radius of the plate.

For FMLs, the Young's modulus E in the above equation may be calculated as follows:

$$E = \frac{E_{Al}h_{Al} + E_f h_f}{h} \quad (2)$$

where E_{Al} and E_f are the Young's moduli of the aluminium alloy and the glass fibre composite, h_{Al} and h_f are the thicknesses of aluminium alloy and glass fibre layers, respectively.

For a square plate with a length and width equal to 'a', the boundary condition is similar to a circular plate with a diameter $\sqrt{2}a$. Therefore, the impact load for a square plate with the above dimensions, should be similar to that for a circular plate with a diameter $\sqrt{2}a$. Based on Eq. (1) and the impact results of a square FML, the load P for a 3/2 square FMLs with length 'a' is assumed to be equal to that for a 3/2 circular FML with a diameter $1.5a$ and expressed as Equation (1) with $C=0.00067$ m and $D=10$ m⁻¹.

For the thick FMLs, the stiffness is underestimated using Eq. (1) which treats these FMLs as isotropic plates, i.e. without considering their laminated nature. To take this into account, the constants C and D in Eq. (1) are reduced to 0.001 m and 10 m⁻¹ for the circular plates and 0.00045 m and 6.7 m⁻¹ for the square plates. Table 1 summarises the values of A, B, C, D in Eq. (1) used for FMLs with different stacking sequences and shapes.

By taking an average of the ratio of the theoretical energy up to peak load to the numerical perforation energy for all of the FMLs, a ratio of approximately 40% is obtained. Therefore, the perforation energy E_p may be estimated by:

$$E_p = \beta \int_0^{\omega_0} P_{peak} d\omega \quad (3)$$

where β is estimated to be 2.5, making the theoretical results agree well with the experimental data.

Table 1 Data for Eq. (1).

	A	B	C (m)	D (m ⁻¹)
2/1 FML square	0.443	0.217	0.00067	10.0
2/1 FML circular	0.443	0.217	0.00150	15.0
3/2 FML square	0.443	0.217	0.00067	10.0
3/2 FML circular	0.443	0.217	0.00150	15.0
4/3 FML square	0.443	0.217	0.00045	6.7
4/3 FML circular	0.443	0.217	0.00100	10.0
5/4 FML square	0.443	0.217	0.00045	6.7
5/4 FML circular	0.443	0.217	0.00100	10.0

Based on the FE simulation results, the peak load and perforation energy of the FMLs subjected to a hemispherical projectile with impact angle α can be estimated using the results of FMLs impacted by a hemispherical projectile at 90° to the surface of the plate:

$$P_A = P_0 \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{180}\right), \quad \alpha \leq 45^\circ \quad (4)$$

and

$$E_A = E_0 \left(1 + \frac{\alpha}{180}\right)^{1.5}, \quad \alpha \leq 45^\circ \quad (5)$$

P_0 and E_0 is the peak load and perforation energy corresponding to $\alpha = 0^\circ$.

The peak load and perforation energy of the FMLs subjected to an oval projectile with a projectile head height H , can be estimated from the results of FMLs impacted by a hemispherical projectile:

$$P_H = P_d / (0.6 + 0.8H/d) \quad (6)$$

and

$$E_H = E_d / (0.6 + 0.8H/d) \quad (7)$$

where $P_{\frac{d}{2}}$ and $E_{\frac{d}{2}}$ are the peak load and perforation energy of FMLs subjected to low velocity impact by a hemispherical projectile with diameter of “ d ” and height of “ $d/2$ ”.

4. Results and discussion

Fig. 3 shows the theoretical load-displacement curves using Eq. (1) and the experimental results for 3/2 FMLs based on 4-ply composite core. As it can be seen, very good correlation is obtained on the load-displacement traces up to the peak load.

Predictions of the load-displacement trace up to peak load are also produced for the 4/3 FMLs based on Eq. (1). Fig. 4 shows the comparisons between the predictions and the experimental results. A reasonable good correlation is obtained, which again indicates that Eq. (1) can be used to predict the peak load of FMLs reasonably well.

Fig. 3. Theoretical and experimental load-displacement curves for 3/2 FML made with different composite cores subjected to low velocity impact.

Theoretical prediction results of peak load using an equation for square targets based on Eq. (1) are compared with the experimental and FE results for 2/1, 3/2, 4/3 and 5/4 FMLs made with different number of plies, target shapes and projectile sizes, which are shown in Fig. 5. Clearly, reasonably good correlation has been obtained.

Fig. 4. Theoretical and experimental load-displacement curves for 4/3 FML made with 4-ply and 8-ply composite layers subjected to low velocity impact.

Fig. 6 compares the perforation energy calculated with the experimental and FE results. In most cases, the difference between the theoretical predictions and the experimental/FE results is within 10 percent.

Fig. 5. Comparison of predicted peak load of FML plates subjected to impact with the corresponding results from tests and FE simulations.

Fig. 7 compares the peak load and perforation energy obtained from FE simulations and Equations (4) and (5), which clearly show quite good correlation.

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Fig. 6. Perforation energy of FML plates (in Table 2) subjected to impact.

Fig. 8 compares the peak load and perforation energy obtained from FE simulations and those from Equations (6) and (7). Clearly, good correlation is obtained, which indicates the reliability of the empirical formulas developed.

The calculation results presented the above have shown overall good agreement with the corresponding experimental results. Therefore, the empirical formulas developed may be used to cover calculations for other stacking sequences and target geometries.

Fig. 7. Comparisons of theoretical and numerical relationship between peak load/perforation energy and projectile impact angle for the 2/1 and 3/2 FMLs based on 4-ply composite cores subjected to low velocity impact, data from FE simulations and Equations (4) and (5).

Fig. 8. Variation of the peak load and perforation energy with the ratio of projectile head height/diameter for 72 mm × 72 mm square 3/2 FMLs based on 4-ply composite cores subjected to low velocity impact, data from FE simulations and Equations (6) and (7).

5 Conclusions

Based on parametric study results using validated computer models, the effects of target size, target thickness, projectile size, shape and striking angle on the low velocity impact response of FMLs have been investigated. The peak load and perforation energy obtained from FE simulations and empirical formulae were compared with experimental results with reasonably good correlation. This covers

circular or square targets of 2/1, 3/2 and 4/3 FMLs of different size impacted by hemispherical projectiles of various diameters.

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